

FATIGUE DAMAGE MECHANISMS OF WOVEN LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

The tensile fatigue damage mechanisms of three unnotched and notched woven laminates (two orthotropic and one quasi-isotropic) were studied. The apparent secant stiffness changes with the cyclic number for both unnotched and notched woven laminated specimens during tensile fatigue test at a fixed ratio of maximum fatigue load to UTS were observed. The observable damage initiation and evolution as a function of the cyclic number were measured directly at the notched specimen surface with a video-camera system. Finally, the microstructure of the specimens after fatigue was analyzed with a microscopy.

The results show that the normalized apparent secant stiffness change curves as a function of cyclic numbers can be divided into three stages. For the first and the second stages in notched specimens and for total life of unnotched specimens, the damage may be mainly characterized by the micro-cracks produced in the resin of interweaving structure and decohesions produced at the interfaces between the resin and the fiber because many acoustic emission signals can be observed during the two stages. But, this type of damages has not been evidently observed and certainly verified with the traditional experimental methods such as radiography and microscopy. Fortunately, the last stage ($N/N_f > 0.4$, the secant stiffness decreases fast) corresponds to the initiation and evolution of the observable damages in notched specimens, and the damage of the last stage for notched specimens was found to be directly observable at the specimen surface with a video camera system. Its propagation is influenced both by the thickness of the continuous plies to 90° and by the stacking sequences, which has been verified by microscopic examinations.

Then, the fatigue strength of these woven composite laminates is dominated by the third stage during which the observable damage develops along the specimen ligament until fracture. During the third stage, a critical dimension at the specimen ligament and a life threshold can be found beyond which a final catastrophic fracture will occur.

Keywords: Composites, Woven laminates, Damage, Fatigue strength, Glass fiber, Epoxy

INTRODUCTION

It is well known that glass fiber reinforced composite materials are not so resistant against fatigue as carbon fiber composites. However, under cyclic loading, the behaviors for woven glass / epoxy laminates are not very well understood in comparison with those for nonwoven laminates. In this paper, the fatigue damage of three woven laminates (two orthotropic and one quasi-isotropic) [1] is discussed.

Most studies on composite material fatigue behaviors have been carried out with the help of phenomenological methods. For the purpose of predicting fatigue life and residual strength, statistic models [2-9] were proposed, because of fatigue behavior dispersion, and can play an important role in

many engineering applications. The parameters in these models, although being obtained with certain statistic methods, for example, the maximum likelihood estimation, are not easy to be determined because of having need of a number of specimens. Especially, the notched laminate fatigue residual strength does not always vary monotonically with the number of cycles [10]. As pointed in [11], it can not be preferably chosen as a parameter describing characteristically the damage mechanisms. Therefore, some researchers considered the apparent secant stiffness changes as the parameters demonstrating damage mechanisms [12-14] and measured these changes under different test conditions [15-18]. However, up to now, due to the complexity for composite materials, a fundamental understanding of the relationship between damage mechanisms and failure modes that dominate the composite fatigue behavior has not yet been established.

In the present paper, at a fixed cyclic load level, the apparent secant stiffness changes as a function of the cyclic number for both unnotched and notched woven composites were measured. The damage initiation and evolution, and the microstructure after fatigue of the laminates were observed.

MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTS

The stacking sequences and the thicknesses for the three woven laminates studied in this paper are shown in Table.1. The warp and woof compositions in the woven ply of the laminates are respectively 82% and 18%. The properties for the woven lamina are shown in Table 2, and the methods to fabricate the specimens and to measure the ultimate static strength were shown in [1].

Table.1 Stacking sequences and thicknesses of three woven laminates studied in the paper

TYPE	DESCRIPTION	STACKING SEQUENCES	THICKNESS
Glass-1	E Glass-weave/Epoxy	[0/0/+45/0/0/-45/90/90]s	3.3 mm
Glass-2	E Glass-weave/Epoxy	[0/+45/0/90/0/-45/90/0]s	3.3 mm
Glass-3	E Glass-weave/Epoxy	[0/0/+45/+45/-45/-45/90/90]s	3.3 mm

Table 2 Properties of the woven ply for the Glass-1, 2, and 3

PROPERTIES	DATA
Longitudinal module E_1	38500 MPa
Transverse module E_2	17600 MPa
Plan shear module G_{12}	4400 MPa
Longitudinal tensile strength X_1	900 MPa
Longitudinal compressive strength X_1'	500 MPa
Transverse tensile strength X_2	70 MPa
Transverse compressive strength X_2'	250 MPa
Plan shear strength X_{12}	80 MPa
Plan Poisson coefficient ν_{12}	0.25

The apparent secant stiffness changes were measured with a gage-length extensometer centered to the notch, whose knife-edges were fixed in V-notches engraved in two thin aluminum tabs bonded at the specimen (see Fig.A(a)). The static secant stiffness for unnotched and notched specimens was periodically determined by interrupting the fatigue tests and by measuring the curves of load vs extensometer strain up to the maximum fatigue loads. In particular, the observable damage initiation and evolution were directly observed and measured at the notched specimen surface with a video-camera system (see Fig.A(b)), and were verified by X-radiography photos. The tensile fatigue tests of the unnotched specimens and notched specimens with a diameter of 5 mm were carried out with INSTRON machine at room temperature and relevant data were acquired by a system piloted with PC-IBM. The acoustic emission was used to detect the damages during the fatigue tests. The stress ratio is equal to 0.1 and the ratio of the maximum fatigue load to UTS is equal to 0.5. The fatigue frequency

is 20 Hz. All test conditions were described in [1].

Fig.A Measurement of apparent secant stiffness and observation of damage at the specimen surfaces

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Secant stiffness changes

Fig.1 Comparison of the normalized secant stiffness changes vs the normalized cyclic numbers between the unnotched and notched specimens: (a) Glass-1; (b) Glass-2; (c) Glass-3

The normalized secant stiffness changes as a function of both unnotched and notched normalized fatigue lives for the laminates have been respectively measured. These measurements indicate that unnotched and notched specimens tend to go through three stages during the fatigue tests. Figs. 1a to 1c show a result comparison between the unnotched and notched specimens respectively for the three laminates. From these figures, it can be seen that the first stage is characterized by a rapid stiffness loss during a short life, and in the second stage the stiffness degradation is much more gradual and takes place over a much longer proportion of the life. During the third stage, the notched stiffness degradation either is much more rapid (Glass-1 and 2) or is much earlier (Glass-3) than the unnotched specimens.

Figs. 2a and 2b show a comparison of the normalized secant stiffness change vs normalized cyclic number among three different stacking sequences respectively for the unnotched and notched specimens. Three stages at the normalized stiffness curve for the quasi-isotropic laminate are much more evident than those for the two orthotropic laminates. The orthotropic laminate Glass-2 (the 90°

plies are separated by the other plies) possesses a greatest residual stiffness and the quasi-isotropic laminate (the fraction of 0° plies is less than that in the others) is of a least residual stiffness, both for unnotched and for notched specimens. A microscopic examination will explain these differences.

Fig.2 Comparison of the normalized secant stiffness changes vs the normalized cyclic numbers between different stacking sequences: (a) unnotched specimens, (b) notched specimens

Initiation and evolution of observable damages

Fig.3 Normalized stiffness decrement, observable damage initiation and evolution with cycle number

Fig.4 Damages observed at the specimen surfaces (X 2.2)

The normalized apparent secant stiffness change (E/E_0) and the size of observable damage region (a) observed at the notched specimen surface were measured at the same time. The latter is normalized by the half specimen width (W). The results obtained have been shown in Fig.3. The damage observed at the notched specimen surface can be shown in Fig.4. The third stage at the normalized apparent stiffness change curves corresponds to the initiation and the evolution of the observable damages, respectively indicated by the three dotted lines A, B and C in Fig.3 for the three laminates. These damages are characterized by the cracks in the plies to 90° , produced adjacent to the hole and contaminating the other plies with a very rapid rate and evolving along the ligament, as indicated in [19]. As concerns the first and the second stages for the notched specimens and the total life for the unnotched specimens, it must be mentioned that the damages produced in the materials are not visually observable at the surfaces but it is certain that many micro-level damages, for example, micro-cracks produced in the resin of interweaving structure and decohesions produced at the interfaces between the resin and the fiber, occur in the materials because many signals can be observed at the acoustic emission scheme during these two stages. But, as indicated in [1], these damages have not been verified by microscopy and X-radiography, even with certain opacities to X-ray, as iodide zinc and

tetrabromoethane.

It can be seen from Fig.3 that the observable damages initialize much earlier in the quasi-isotropic laminate (Glass-3) than in the others (Glass-1,2); by contrast, they initialize much later in Glass-2

Fig.5 Fatigue damages observed with radiography: (a) Glass-1; (b) Glass-2; (c) Glass-3

Fig.6 Evolution at the specimen surface of observable damages: (a) Glass-1; (b) Glass-2; (c) Glass-3

than the others (Glass-1,3). For a same life fraction, it is Glass-3 (quasi-isotropic) that is of a greater damage zone size, as verified with X-radiography photos in Fig.5. During the fatigue tests, any evident delamination adjacent to the free-edges can not be observed in the laminates. A critical dimension of damaged region along the notched specimen ligament and a critical value of the normalized life can be determined, as shown in Fig.6. Beyond these critical values, a final catastrophic fracture will occur immediately.

A microscopic observation can show the damage evolution in the laminates. One can see from Fig.7 that the damage propagation must overcome much more obstacles paid by the interfaces between the plies to 90° and the other plies in Glass-2 (shown in Fig.7b) than in the other laminates so that the route passed by the damage propagation in this laminate is much more sinuous than that in the other laminates. This is the reason why this laminate has both a greater residual stiffness during the fatigue tests, as shown in the preceding figures, and a longer fatigue life, as shown in [19].

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig.7 Microscopy observation (X44,N/Nf=0.85;<----->: thickness direction) (a) Glass-1; (b) Glass-2; (c) Glass-3

CONCLUSIONS

The normalized apparent secant stiffness change curves as a function of cyclic numbers can be divided into three stages for three unnotched and notched woven laminates (two orthotropic and one quasi-isotropic).

During the first and the second stages of the apparent secant stiffness changes in the notched specimens and during the total life of the unnotched specimens, damages may be mainly characterized by the micro-cracks produced in the resin of interweaving structure and decohesions produced at the interfaces between the resins and the fibers because many acoustic emission signals can be observed during these two stages although these signals do not possess a good reproducibility. However, this type of damage has not been observed evidently and verified certainly with the traditional experimental methods such as radiography and microscopy in our study. How to detect evidently and verified certainly these damages is a problem to be solved.

Fortunately, the last stage ($N/N_f > 0.4$, the secant stiffness decreases fast) corresponds to the initiation and evolution of the observable damages in notched specimens. During the last stage, the fatigue damages in the notched specimens were found to be observable directly at the specimen surface with a video camera system. Their propagation is influenced both by the thickness of the continuous plies to 90° and by the stacking sequences, which has been verified both by microscopy examination and by X-radiography.

Then, the fatigue resistance of these woven composite laminates is dominated by the third stage during which the observable damages develop along the specimen ligament until fracture. During the third stage, a critical dimension at the specimen ligament and a life threshold can be found beyond which a final catastrophic fracture for the specimens will occur immediately.

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